

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

OPTIMALITY TYPE CONDITION OF THE PONTRHGIN MAXSIMUM PRINSIPLE IN THE PROBLEM OF CONTROL OF LINEAR FRACTIONALORDER DIFFERENCE EQUATIONS

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Abstract

The problem of optimal control of systems of linear two- dimensional difference equations of fractional order is considered. A number of optimality conditions are established.

Keywords: admissible control, optimal control, open set, fractional order difference equation, fractional operator, linearized maximum principle, fractionalsum, necessary and sufficient condition.

1. Introduction

Fractional calculus plays an important role in many areas of science and technology. It is known that (see, for example, [1]) the fractional integro-differential calculus originates from a discussion in correspondence between G. Lopital and G. Leibniz about the meaning of the derivative of order 1/2. But the idea of using a fractional difference appeared relatively recently (see, for example, [2-5]).

Fractional calculus also finds application in optimal control problemsdescribed by difference equations of fractional order [6-8].

Based on theoretical and practical applications, the development of a qualitative theory of optimal control problems described by various fractional-order difference equations is also relevant. Note that the theory of necessary optimality conditions for optimal control problems described by different fractional-order difference equations has been very little developed.

In [9], a representation of the solution of a boundary value problem for a system of linear nonhomogeneous two-dimensional fractional order difference equations is obtained.

In this paper, for the considered equation, the problem of optimal control underthe assumption that the control function enters the boundary condition, and thefunctional is linear is studied.

A necessary and sufficient optimality condition in the form of a discrete maximum principle is proved.

In the case of a non-linear but convex performance functional, a sufficient optimality condition is proved.

2. Statement of the problem.

Consider the problem of minimizing the linear functional

$$S(u) = c'a(x_1) + d'z(t_1, x_1) \quad (1)$$

under restrictions

$$u(x) \in U \subset R^r, x \in X, \{x_0, x_0 + 1, \dots, x_1 - 1\}.$$

$$\Delta^\alpha z(t + 1, x + 1) = \quad (2)$$

$$= A(t, x)z(t, x) + B(t, x)z(t + 1, x) + C(t, x)z(t, x + 1) + D(t, x), \quad (3)$$

$$z(t_0, x) = a(x), x \in X \cup x_1, \quad (4)$$

$$z(t, x_0) = b(t), \quad t \in T \cup t_1, T = \{t_0, t_0 + 1, \dots, t_1 - 1\} \quad (5)$$

$$a(x_0) = b(t_0) = a_0,$$

$$\Delta^\beta a(x + 1) =$$

$$= K(x)a(x) + g(x, u(x)),$$

$$x \in X,$$

$$a(x_0) = a_0, \quad (6)$$

Here $A(t, x)$, $B(t, x)$, $C(t, x)$, $K(x)$ are given $(n \times n)$ - discrete matrix functions, $D(t, x)$ - given n - dimensional discrete vector function, $b(t)$ given discrete vector function, a_0, t_0, t_1, x_0, x_1 are givens, $g(x, u)$ -given continuous by u for all x

n – dimensional vector function, $u(x)$ – r –dimensional vector function of control actions with values from a given non–empty and bounded set U (admissible control), n d – given n –dimensional constant vectors, and $\Delta^\alpha z(t, x)$, $\Delta^\beta a(x)$, $0 < \alpha, \beta \leq 1$ fractional order operator by orders α and β (see for example, [2-5]).

An admissible control that delivers the minimum value to the functional (1) under constraints (2)-(6) is called optimal controls.

3. The formula for the increment of the quality functional.

Let (x) , $\bar{u}(x) = u(x) + \Delta u(x)$ – two admissible controls. Through $((x)$,

$z(t, x)$), $(\bar{a}(x) = a(x) + \Delta a(x), \bar{z}(t, x) = z(t, x) + \Delta z(t, x))$ denotes the solutions of system (2)–(6) corresponding to them. Then the increment of functional (1) takes the form

$$\Delta S(u) = c' \Delta a(x_1) + d' \Delta z(t_1, x_1). \quad (7)$$

Here $\Delta(x)$, $\Delta z(t, x)$ are solutions to problems

$$\Delta^\beta \Delta a(x) = K(x) \Delta a(x) + \Delta_{\bar{u}(x)} g[x], \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta a(x_0) = 0. \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta^\alpha \Delta z(t+1, x+1) = A(t, x) \Delta z(t, x) + B(t, x) \Delta z(t+1, x) + C(t, x) \Delta z(t, x+1), \quad (10)$$

$$\Delta z(t_0, x) = \Delta a(x), x \in X \cup x_1, \quad (11)$$

$$\Delta z(t, x_0) = 0, t \in T \cup t_1, \quad (12)$$

respectively.

Here, according to definition,

$$\Delta_{\bar{u}(x)} g[x] = g(x, \bar{u}(x)) - g(x, u(x))$$

As can be seen, equations (8) and (10) are systems of linear nonhomogeneous difference equations with respect to $\Delta(x)$ и $\Delta z(t, x)$ correspondingly.

Takes place [2]

Theorem 1. Solution $y(t)$ systems of linear nonhomogeneous difference equations of fractional order

$$\Delta^\alpha y(t+1) = A(t)y(t) + g(t)$$

with initial conditions

$$y(t) = y_0.$$

admits representation

$$y(t) = y_0 \prod_{j=t_0}^{t-1} [1 + R_\alpha(t-1, j)A(j)] + \sum_{j=t_0}^{t-1} R_\alpha(t-1, j)g(j) \prod_{k=j+1}^{t-1} [1 + R_\alpha(t-1, k)A(k)] \quad (13)$$

where

$$R_\alpha(t, j) = \binom{t-j+\alpha-1}{t-j}.$$

A binomial coefficient $\binom{\alpha}{n}$ is determined by the formula

$$\binom{a}{n} = \begin{cases} \frac{\Gamma(a+1)}{\Gamma(a-n+1)\Gamma(n+1)}, & n > 0, \\ 1, & n = 0, \\ 0, & n < 0. \end{cases}$$

$$x^{(y)} = \frac{\Gamma(x+1)}{\Gamma(x+1-y)}$$

Here for any $x, y \in R$, where Γ – the gamma function for which holds the identity $\Gamma(x+1) = x\Gamma(x)$.

By Theorem 1, the solution of equation (8) with initial conditions (9) is represented as

$$\Delta a(x) = \sum_{j=x_0}^{x-1} R_\beta(x-1, j) \Delta_{\bar{u}(j)} g[j] \times \\ \times \prod_{m=j+1}^{x-1} [1 + R_\beta(x-1, m) K(m)].$$

Introduce the following notation

$$\Phi(x, j) = R_\beta(x-1, j) \prod_{m=j+1}^{x-1} [1 + R_\beta(x-1, m) K(m)], \quad (15)$$

then

$$\Delta a(x) = \sum_{j=x_0}^{x-1} \Phi(x, j) \Delta_{\bar{u}(j)} g[j] \quad (16)$$

It follows from the result of [9] follows

Теорема 2. Solution $z(t, x)$ of the boundary value problem (3)-(5) for a system of linear 2D fractional order difference equations can be represented in the following form

$$z(t, x) = a(x_0) + \sum_{j=t_0}^{t-1} R_\alpha(t-1, x-1; j, x_0-1) \\ \times C(j, x_0-1) b(j) + \sum_{s=x_0}^{x-1} R_\alpha(t_0-1, x-1; t_0-1, s) B(t_0-1, s) a(s) + \\ + \sum_{j=t_0}^{t-1} \sum_{s=x_0}^{x-1} R_\alpha(t-1, j; s) D(j, s). \quad (17)$$

Here

$$R_\alpha(t-1, x-1; j, s) = \\ = \binom{t-j+\alpha-1}{t-j} \binom{x-s+\alpha-1}{x-s},$$

where $R_\alpha(t-1, x-1; j, s)$ is solution to the following problem:

$$\begin{aligned}
R_\alpha(t-1, x-1; j, s)A(j, s) &= -R_\alpha(t-1, x-1; j-1, s)B(j-1, s) - \\
&- R_\alpha(t-1, x-1; j, s-1)C(j, s-1), \quad j = t-1, \dots, t_0, s = x-1, \dots, x_0, \\
R_\alpha(t, x; t-1, x-1) &= E.
\end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

Then it is clear that,

$$\Delta z(t, x) = \sum_{s=x_0}^{x-1} R_\alpha(t-1, x-1; t_0-1, s) B(t_0-1, s) \Delta a(s). \tag{19}$$

Substituting (16) into (19) we will get:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta z(t, x) &= \sum_{s=x_0}^{x-1} R_\alpha(t-1, x-1; t_0-1, s) B(t_0-1, s) \Delta a(s) \\
&= \sum_{s=x_0}^{x-1} R_\alpha(t-1, x-1; t_0-1, s) B(t_0-1, s) \sum_{j=x_0}^{x-1} \Phi(x, j) \Delta_{\bar{u}(j)} g[j].
\end{aligned}$$

Assuming

$$Q_1(t, x, s) = \sum_{\tau=s+1}^{x-1} R_\alpha(t-1, x-1; t_0-1, \tau) B(t_0-1, \tau) \Phi(\tau, s) \tag{20}$$

we get that

$$\Delta z(t, x) = \sum_{s=x_0}^{x-1} Q_1(t, x, s) \Delta_{\bar{u}(s)} g[s]. \tag{21}$$

Taking into account relations (16) and (21), the increment formula (7) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta S(u) &= c' \Delta a(x_1) + d' \Delta z(t_1, x_1) = \\
&= \sum_{x=x_0}^{x_1-1} c' \Phi(x_1, x) \Delta_{\bar{u}(x)} g[x] + \sum_{x=x_0}^{x_1-1} d' Q_1(t_1, x_1, x) \Delta_{\bar{u}(x)} g[x] = \\
&= \sum_{x=x_0}^{x_1-1} [c' \Phi(x_1, x) + d' Q_1(t_1, x_1, x)] \Delta_{\bar{u}(x)} g[x].
\end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

Assuming

$$\begin{aligned}
p(x) &= - [c' \Phi(x_1, x) + d' Q_1(t_1, x_1, x)] \\
M'(x, u, p) &= p' g(x, u) \\
\Delta_{\bar{u}(x)} M[x] &= p' \Delta_{\bar{u}(x)} g[x],
\end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

relation (22) is written as

$$\Delta S(u) = - \sum_{x=x_0}^{x_1-1} \Delta_{\bar{u}(x)} M[x]. \tag{24}$$

It can be proved that the vector function (x) defined by formula (23) is a solution of equation

$$p(x-1) = - [c' \Phi(x_1, x-1) + d' Q_1(t_1, x_1, x-1)]. \tag{25}$$

Next, from (19) we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned}
& Q_1(t_1, x_1, x - 1) = \\
& = R_\alpha(t_1 - 1, x_1 - 1; t_0 - 1, x)Q_1(t_1, x_1, x).
\end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

Taking into account (15), (26) in (25) we have

$$p(x - 1) = p(x) + \psi(t_0 - 1, x)B'(t_0 - 1, x), \tag{27}$$

where by definition

$$\psi(t, x) = -R'_\alpha(t_1, x_1; t, x)d.$$

From (25) follows that

$$p(x_1 - 1) = -c. \tag{28}$$

Further, using (28) it is shown that $\psi(t, x)$, defined by the formula

$$\psi(t, x) = -R'_\alpha(t_1 - 1, x_1 - 1; t, x)d,$$

is a solution to the boundary value problem

$$\begin{aligned}
& \psi(t - 1, x - 1) = A'(t, x)\psi(t, x) + \\
& \quad -B'(t, x)\psi(t - 1, x) - C'(t, x)\psi(t, x - 1), \\
& \psi(t_1 - 1, x - 1) = B'(t_1 - 1, x)\psi(t_1 - 1, x), \\
& \psi(t - 1, x_1 - 1) = C'(t, x_1 - 1)\psi(t, x_1 - 1), \\
& \psi(t_1 - 1, x_1 - 1) = -d.
\end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

4. Condition of optimality.

With the help of representation (24) it is proved

Theorem 3. For the optimality of an admissible control $(x), x \in X$ in the problem (1)-(5) necessary and sufficient that the equality

$$\max_{v \in U} M(\xi, v, p(\xi)) = M(\xi, u(\xi), p(\xi)), \tag{30}$$

is satisfied for everyone $\xi \in X$.

Proof. Necessity: Suppose, that (x) optimal control. Then it follows from the increment formula (24) that for any admissible control $\bar{u}(x) = u(x) + \Delta u(x)$

$$\sum_{x=x_0}^{x_1-1} \Delta_{\bar{u}(x)} M[x] \leq 0. \tag{31}$$

Using arbitrariness $\bar{u}(x)$, define it as follows

$$\bar{u}(x) = \begin{cases} v, & x = \xi \in X, \\ u(x), & x \neq \xi \in X, \end{cases}$$

where $\xi \in X$ arbitrary point, $v \in U$ arbitrary vector.

Then inequality (31) takes the form:

$$\Delta_v M[\xi] \leq 0.$$

Hence, due to the arbitrariness $v \in U$ and $\xi \in X$ follows the maximum condition (30).

Let us proceed to the proof of the sufficiency of the maximum condition (30).

Suppose that for an admissible control (x) the Pontryagin maximum condition (30) is satisfied. It follows from this, that for any $\xi \in X$, $\bar{u}(\xi) = v \in U$,

$$\Delta_{\bar{u}(\xi)} M[\xi] \leq 0.$$

Hence, due to the arbitrariness $\xi \in X$ follows, that

$$\sum_{\xi=x_0}^{x_1-1} \Delta_{\bar{u}(\xi)} M[\xi] \leq 0.$$

Taking into account this inequality, from (24) we obtain that for any admissible control $\bar{u}(x)$

$$\Delta S(u) = S(\bar{u}) - S(u) \geq 0, \text{ т. е.}$$

$$S(\bar{u}) \geq S(u).$$

It follows from the last relation that the control (x) is the optimal control.

This proves the sufficiency of the discrete condition for the Pontryagin maximum.

5. The case of a convex performance criterion.

Let's study more general case. Consider the problem of minimizing the functional

$$S(u) = \varphi_1(a(x_1)) + \varphi_2(z(t_1, x_1)), \quad (32)$$

under restrictions (2)-(5).

Here $\varphi_1(a)$, $\varphi_2(z)$ – are given continuously differentiable and convex scalar functions.

In the case of problem (1)-(5), (32), the increment of functional (32) corresponding to admissible controls (x) , $\bar{u}(x) = u(x) + \Delta u(x)$ using the Taylor formula can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta S(u) = S(\bar{u}) - S(u) &= \frac{\partial \varphi_1(a(x_1))}{\partial a} \Delta a(x_1) + \\ &+ \frac{\partial \varphi_2(z(t_1, x_1))}{\partial z} \Delta z(t_1, x_1) + o_1(\|\Delta a(x_1)\|) + o_2(\|z(t_1, x_1)\|), \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

where the quantities $o_i(\cdot)$, $i = 1, 2$ are determined from expansions

$$\varphi_1(\bar{a}(x_1)) - \varphi_1(a(x_1)) = \frac{\partial \varphi_1(a(x_1))}{\partial a} \Delta a(x_1) + o_1(\|\Delta a(x_1)\|),$$

$$\varphi_2(\bar{z}(t_1, x_1)) - \varphi_2(z(t_1, x_1)) = \frac{\partial \varphi_2(z(t_1, x_1))}{\partial z} \Delta z(t_1, x_1) + o_2(\|z(t_1, x_1)\|).$$

Using representations (16), (21), the increment formula (33) is transformed to the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta S(u) &= \\ &= \sum_{x=x_0}^{x_1-1} \frac{\partial \varphi_1(a(x_1))}{\partial a} \Phi(x, x_1) \Delta_{\bar{u}(x)} g[x] + \sum_{x=x_0}^{x_1-1} \frac{\partial \varphi_2(z(t_1, x_1))}{\partial z} Q_1(t_1, x_1, x) \times \\ &\quad \times \Delta_{\bar{u}(x)} g[x] + o_1(\|\Delta a(x_1)\|) + o_2(\|z(t_1, x_1)\|) = \\ &= \sum_{x=x_0}^{x_1-1} \left[\frac{\partial \varphi_1(a(x_1))}{\partial a} \Phi(x, x_1) + \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{\partial \varphi_2(z(t_1, x_1))}{\partial z} Q_1(t_1, x_1, x) \right] \Delta_{\bar{u}(x)} g[x] + \\ &\quad + o_1(\|\Delta a(x_1)\|) + o_2(\|z(t_1, x_1)\|). \end{aligned} \quad (34)$$

Assuming

$$p'(x) = - \left[\frac{\partial \varphi_1(a(x_1))}{\partial a} \Phi(x, x_1) + \frac{\partial \varphi_2(z(t_1, x_1))}{\partial z} Q_1(t_1, x_1, x) \right],$$

$$M(x, u, p) = p' g(x, u), \quad (35)$$

$$\psi(t, x) = -R'_\alpha(t_1, x_1; t, x) \frac{\partial \varphi_2(z(t_1, x_1))}{\partial z}, \quad (36)$$

$$\Delta S(u) = - \sum_{x=x_0}^{x_1-1} \Delta_{\bar{u}(x)} M[x] + o_1(\|\Delta a(x_1)\|) + o_2(\|z(t_1, x_1)\|). \quad (37)$$

From (35), (36), using (15), (18) we get that (x) and $\psi(t, x)$ are solutions of following problems, correspondingly:

$$p(x-1) = p(x) + \psi(t_0 - 1, x)B'(t_0 - 1, x), \quad (38)$$

$$p(x_1 - 1) = -\frac{\partial \varphi_1(a(x_1))}{\partial a}.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(t-1, x-1) &= A'(t, x) \psi(t, x) - \\ &- B'(t, x) \psi(t-1, x) - (t, x) \psi(t, x-1), \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

$$\psi(t_1 - 1, x - 1) = B'(t_1 - 1, x) \psi(t_1 - 1, x),$$

$$\psi(t-1, x_1 - 1) = C'(t, x_1 - 1) \psi(t, x_1 - 1),$$

$$\psi(t_1 - 1, x_1 - 1) = -\frac{\partial \varphi_2(z(t_1, x_1))}{\partial z}.$$

Due to the convexity of the functions $\varphi_1(a), \varphi_2(z)$ it's clear that

$$o_1 \|\Delta a(x_1)\| \geq 0, o_2 \|z(t_1, x_1)\| \geq 0.$$

Therefore, from (37) follows the inequality

$$\Delta S(u) \geq -\sum_{x=x_0}^{x_1-1} \Delta_{\bar{u}(x)} M[x]. \quad (40)$$

From relation (40) follows

Theorem 4. For the optimality of an admissible control (x) in problem (1)-(5), (32) enough that the inequality

$$\sum_{x=x_0}^{x_1-1} \Delta_{v(x)} M[x] \leq 0, \quad (41)$$

Is satisfied for every $(x) \in U, x \in X$.

Proof. Let an admissible control (x) satisfies relation (41). Then inequality

(40) implies that for any admissible control $v(x)$

$$S(v) - S(u) \geq 0.$$

The last relation means the optimality of the admissible control (x) . This completes the proof of Theorem 4.

Thus, in two cases it was possible to prove the necessary and sufficient optimality conditions in the form of the discrete Pontryagin maximum principle.

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